

MARINEWIND

Market Uptake Measures of Floating Offshore Wind Technology Systems (FOWTs)

1/11/2022 – 31/10/2025

Call: HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-02

Project 101075572 — MARINEWIND

T1.3_Spain Lab 3rd Co-creation Workshop Report

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Document history

Issue date	Version	Changes made / Reason for this issue
12/06/2024	00	First edition

TABLE OF CONTENTS

TABLE OF CONTENTS	2
1 EVENT DETAILS.....	3
2 OVERVIEW OF CONTRIBUTIONS AND INTERVENTIONS BY THE SPEAKERS.....	5
2.1 ASSESSING THE CURRENT REGULATORY FRAMEWORK OF MARINE WIND ENERGY.....	5
2.2 SOCIOECONOMIC AND ENVIRONMENTAL VISION OF MARINE WIND ENERGY.....	7
2.3 FINANCIAL AND TECHNOLOGICAL STATE OF MARINE WIND ENERGY.....	8
3 ROUNDTABLES TOPICS OVERVIEW	10
4 CO-CREATION ACTIVITIES.....	11
5 SUMMARY OF IDENTIFIED BARRIERS AND ENABLERS	15

1 EVENT DETAILS

EVENT LOCATION: Arenys de Mar, Catalunya

EVENT DATE: 12th June 2024 (from 9.30 AM to 2:30 PM)

EVENT TITLE: Barriers and Enablers in The Development of Floating Offshore Wind in Spain

TYPE OF EVENT: Physical

CATEGORY OF THE EVENT: Co-creation Workshop

EVENT AFFILIATION: European Maritime Day

LEAD ORGANISER: Sener

CO-ORGANISERS: JustWind4All

LANGUAGE: Spanish, Catalan, and English

CONCEPT: The third co-creation workshop in Spain focused on discussing and validating the barriers and enablers of Floating Offshore Wind Technology identified by MARINEWIND from M1 to M18. As part of initiative of the European Maritime Day in my country, the workshop was held at the House of Fishers in Arenys de Mar, very close to Barcelona (Catalonia). This place was chosen because of its location, as the main idea was to bring together all the information from the previous co-creation workshops in Roses and Ferrol, which are places close to future floating offshore wind farms. In this case, the idea was to find a neutral place to discuss all previous aspects. The workshop was divided into three main parts, divided into three main topics:

- Topic 1: Regulatory framework for offshore wind energy
- Topic 2: Socio-economic and environmental vision of offshore wind energy
- Topic 3: Financial and technological state of offshore wind energy

Each table was conducted by a member of MARINEWIND, to explain all the information reached out by the research of the project and also through all the co-creation workshops in all the geographies. Then, participants had the opportunity to listen to presentations by experts in each topic and to take part in debates that promoted an enriching exchange of ideas. This segment allowed for deeper discussions on different aspects and different perspectives regarding the implementation of offshore wind energy in Spain.

OBJECTIVES: To discuss barriers and facilitators to offshore wind deployment in Spain, and specifically in Catalunya.

TARGET AUDIENCE: The participation included representatives of the 5-Helix stakeholders' groups:

- Industry: FOWT installation developers, engineering companies, fisheries, local traders, etc.
- Civil Society: civil society organisations, renewable organisations, etc.
- Academia: scientific community and public/private research organisations.
- Public Authorities: Galician and local government.
- Green Innovation: ecologists, environmental organisations and green cooperatives.

PARTICIPANTS OF YOUR EVENT: 40 participants

5-HELIX STAKEHOLDERS IN THE WORKSHOP

- Civil Society
- Academia
- Green Innovation
- Industry
- Public Authorities

Figure 1 Participants overview

2 OVERVIEW OF CONTRIBUTIONS AND INTERVENTIONS BY THE SPEAKERS

The event was inaugurated by the Mayor of Arenys de Mar, who welcomed the participants and officially opened the session. The selection of speakers was made with the intention of ensuring a balanced representation of the 5-helix stakeholders and topics under analysis by MARINEWIND: policy measures, societal engagement and environmental impact, financial solutions, techno-economic implications, and commercialization of FOWT. Furthermore, the speakers' participation was organized into three distinct categories:

2.1 Assessing the current regulatory framework of Marine Wind Energy

Juan Ramon Ayuso, Head of the Wind and Marine Energy Department of the Institute for Energy Diversification and Saving (IDAE)

On behalf of IDAE, it works with stakeholders in the implementation of floating offshore wind, **promoting a framework that facilitates investment through coordination measures, transparency, and access to information.** The blue economy, which is important for the European Union, is particularly prominent in Spain, which has more than 1 million km² of waters and contributes 17.5% to this economy, making it a key source of growth.

Maritime spatial management plans (MSMPs) aim to reconcile the exploitation of the sea with the protection of 30% of marine areas. Initial zones are identified for further detailed study (suitable in principle at the planning level) and are renewed every 6 years. Areas have been identified as suitable for offshore wind development, covering 0.45% of the maritime terrestrial area.

It is essential to **develop regulatory measures and adapt the administrative framework to facilitate investment**, with a process subject to public consultation and the establishment of an economic franchise essential for the development of offshore wind. This development **must take into account social and environmental sustainability**, evaluating these qualities in the projects and making visible the loss of profit resulting from this implementation, emphasizing the execution of the Roadmap.

Another idea is **making Spain a benchmark for testing new prototypes and solutions**: The proposal is to establish a flexible and agile framework to make Spain a benchmark for testing new prototypes and solutions in renewable energy, in a real testing environment. A total of 23 applications were submitted, most of them for research, with a focus on floating offshore wind and wave energy projects. 127 million has been allocated to six areas: the Mediterranean, the Basque Country, Galicia, Valencia, the Canary Islands and Catalonia. The PLEMCAT project is particularly important in this context, with €30 million allocated to PLEMCAT and approximately €50 million for other projects in the three positions (such as HiveLab, etc.). "It could be unique in the world."

Lluís Pinós, president of the energy commission of EIC (Industrial Engineers of Catalonia)

The College of Engineers is a strong supporter of all renewable energies, aware of climate change and the need for decarbonisation. Long-term studies show that there is a great need for energy, as in

Catalonia, where 62 GW are forecast. Due to the limited space for wind energy in Catalonia, all available space must be used.

The first problem identified is bureaucratic red tape, which hinders progress and delays projects. Large projects have a significant social impact, particularly on vulnerable groups and sectors such as tourism, in addition to the environmental impact. In such cases, compensatory measures are essential. Pinós said that it is vital to consider the **infrastructure for power transmission**, including how it will be connected to the grid. **Economic guarantees** also need to be considered.

The College of Engineers has made allegations about the regulatory framework, pointing to the lack of **planning for grid connection and interconnection with France**. The lack of field data prolongs study periods. The **regulatory framework should strike a balance between economic and non-economic criteria**, with a greater weight given to non-economic criteria, such as technical and socioeconomic criteria, which should represent almost 70% (now in Spain is 30%). Technologies are not yet mature and carry risks, so technical assessments should include more of the voice of experts from the College, who have the necessary knowledge on the subject. Pinós emphasized that with the current pace, it would be difficult to reach the target of 62 GW by 2050 (the decarbonization goal). Additionally, they propose eliminating the risk premium since the technology is not mature. In the technical evaluation committee (in the Royal Decree), they lack voting rights in competitive processes, highlighting the absence of professional colleges.

Raquel Juan, MARINEWIND Director

In order to maximize the results of floating offshore wind projects, it is essential to increase the sharing of best practice and improve the creation of synergies. However, there is a perception that FOWTs are an obstacle to other uses of the sea, which, together with regulatory uncertainty, reduces their attractiveness to investors. In addition, complex permitting processes and a lack of marine spatial planning make it difficult to implement these projects. There are also problems with the division of responsibilities between public and private entities, and current infrastructure is not adequate to support FOWT.

To address these challenges, it is recommended to invest in technological research, establish clear support policies and plan for the long term. It is essential to open up the flexibility market for offshore wind energy and to increase social acceptance by promoting the coexistence of different uses of the sea and integrating FOWT into the socio-economic fabric through training and education programs. Collaboration between developers and learning from successful projects around the world are key strategies.

Measures to support the industry include the implementation of a single EU-wide authorisation procedure, in line with coordinated marine spatial planning. Sites for pre-commercial and demonstration projects need to be identified and clear support policies developed, such as Contracts for Difference (CFD) and Power Purchase Agreements. In addition, the development of onshore and offshore grids to manage high levels of renewable energy should be encouraged.

2.2 Socioeconomic and Environmental vision of Marine Wind Energy

Juan Ramón Vidal, Founder and Director of Asociaciones Estratégicas TECNOAMBIENTE S.L.

At present, there is a large amount of information and a remarkable capacity for prospecting, which is an advantage for the development of wind projects. Eight environmental receptors of wind farms have been identified, which should be taken into account, especially when moving away from the coast to avoid problems near homes. The environmental and social aspects must go hand in hand: birds and bats, marine fauna, pelagic fauna, biodiversity, fisheries and navigation, socio-economic, agriculture and livestock, and impacts on terrestrial and fluvial ecosystems. Additionally, the visual impact should also be considered among the general impacts, although floating technology would notably mitigate this problem. The environmental and social aspects must go hand in hand.

The level of detail highlights the current cartographic capability, emphasizing optimism about the situation in environmental analysis. A major obstacle is public opinion, which is so influential that it can cause developers to abandon projects. To avoid this, studies are carried out to identify stakeholder concerns. Efforts are made to provide a "customized" response to each stakeholder, who has different concerns, in order to establish appropriate corrective and mitigating measures for each of them. Many wind farms have been installed, including in tourist areas, and it is important to understand what has happened and what the impact has been.

Although the environmental part is well understood and no project will be built against this, it is now crucial to **integrate communication with stakeholders** to address their concerns and ensure the success of the project.

Victor Ledo, Secretary General of CCOO Industry of Galicia

Victor agrees with his colleagues about the importance of the environmental aspect of these projects. He emphasizes potential improvement in terms of visual impact that floating technology brings, as it enhances the installation of wind turbines further from the shore, in places where they are barely visible.

There is a lot of experience in the socio-economic aspects, and it is necessary to **emphasize the industrialization of the country**, as well as energy and industrial independence. Electrification presents risks in terms of energy storage. Fishing, particularly the trawling sector (which generates the maximum impact), is one of the major opponents to the development of offshore wind technology. It is important to offer acceptable compensation, as envisaged in the roadmap. **"The offshore wind industry is not just an opportunity but a necessity"** Ledo emphasise.

Photovoltaics cannot fully meet energy needs, but offshore wind can. In Galicia, there are industrial groups that have started to produce components for offshore wind. **Non-economic aspects must be given greater weight**, and the **value chain must be committed to employment**. It is also necessary to plan the capacity of fleets to recycle wind turbines. Ledo also mentioned the steel industry sector (Alcoa Plant), which needs to secure a significant supply of energy at competitive prices (through

renewable PPAs) for its viability. Offshore wind could fulfil this need, considering that the plant consumes approximately one-third of the energy generated in Galicia.

Sara, project engineer in the offshore wind energy department of Sener.

The main barriers to the deployment of floating wind turbines (FOWT) include the negative impact on tourism, as the loss of visitors due to the visual impact affects tourism revenues and obstructs recreational routes and activities. In the fishing sector, reduced income, loss of employment and job security, increased costs and gear conflicts are major challenges. In the property sector, the risk of accidents caused by operation and maintenance vessels crossing shipping lanes and the impact on cultural heritage are additional obstacles.

To manage these conflicts, clear and transparent communication about the potential visual impact of FOWTs is essential. Identifying priority areas at an appropriate distance from the coast can minimise these impacts. Facilitating recreational boating access to designated offshore wind farm (OWF) areas and applying best practices in community engagement, including active community involvement, equitable sharing of economic benefits, and public awareness and education programmes, are key strategies. Government support and environmental research are also critical.

The development of local supply chains, the promotion of re-industrialisation and the creation of local skilled jobs are key factors. Specialised training and education related to FOWT should be a priority to prepare the workforce. Implementing compensation mechanisms and working with affected communities, as well as trial periods to evaluate the technology, will help alleviate concerns.

Generating positive GVA and reducing electricity tariffs are important objectives to increase the acceptance of FOWTs. Compatibility of use with other maritime activities and the development of communication platforms will improve cooperation and efficiency. Co-design of shipping routes and assessment of navigational risks in maritime spatial planning are essential strategies to ensure safety and minimise conflicts.

Needs and recommendations include adequate knowledge of interactions with the marine environment and deep-sea ecosystems. It is essential to develop sound Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) criteria and cumulative impact methodology. Comprehensive criteria, standardised procedures and best practices are needed to ensure project effectiveness and sustainability. The selection of appropriate sites and the application of mitigation measures will help to minimise negative impacts and facilitate coexistence with other maritime activities.

2.3 Financial and Technological state of Marine Wind Energy

Pau Morales-Fusco, Commercial Coordinator of Port de Tarragona

The Port of Tarragona needs to invest in the development of renewable energy and address its main challenges. A key challenge is its **dependence on hydrocarbons**, as 60% of the port is linked to the petrochemical centre, the economic engine of southern Catalonia. It is necessary to change this

dependence and diversify the sectors that supply the port, given that the current model has an expiration date. They aim for a port associated with the energy transition.

The port has the space and various investments to increase its surface area in the short term and define new uses. The strengths of the port, mainly industrial, and its capacity to transfer employment from petrochemicals to renewable energy production are evaluated. It analyses how to extend the life of the port and its role in attracting jobs and investment, with the aim of serving not just one but several wind farms.

The Port of Tarragona is strongly committed to the sector and has the capacity for investment. The technology to be employed in the facility has not yet been finalized. Progress is being made on projects and in **understanding port logistics**. Current discussions are in an evolutionary stage, focusing on precise process understanding necessary for infrastructure development, particularly the construction of the dock.

Internally, the port is advancing its plans. The most developed project is in France, but Tarragona aims to take a leading position, targeting an optimistic start date of 2027. Two potential docks are under consideration, one of which exceeds 20 hectares in size. One project is well advanced, while environmental approval is pending for the other.

Jesus Andese Ferreiro, Director of CaixaBank

Jesús Andese, heads the energy infrastructure financing team, which faces significant internal challenges. Managing renewable energy projects without a proper transmission grid is complex. The team has been actively financing offshore wind projects since 2014, starting in the Netherlands and expanding investments to 26 projects, primarily in the UK, as well as in France, Germany, and the USA. It's noteworthy that all these projects involved fixed technology, but CaixaBank is open to finance floating technology with the properly technology & project technical due diligence.

To support developers, clarity and establishment of all aspects discussed by the speakers are crucial. **Stability is paramount; energy generation is futile without proper evacuation capabilities.** Given the diverse energy mix in Catalonia and Spain, careful planning and project implementation are essential.

CaixaBank is **committed to achieving neutrality by 2050**. The team focuses on two main lines: renewables and transmission networks. From their experience, project timelines are often miscalculated and seldom met. Economic viability must be clear due to high investments with recovery periods of 18-20 years. For a project to be financeable, **legal certainty is imperative**. Long-term financing hinges on clarity across all details and a clear revenue visibility. CaixaBank reaffirms its commitment to these asset types but emphasizes the necessity of a stable environment.

Highlighting the potential challenges, an increase in electricity demand (as projected) coupled with transmission grid issues could lead to a critical scenario, even without nuclear shutdowns. Hence, massive renewable implementation becomes imperative. Regarding the legal framework, both in Spain and Catalonia, there is still work to be done.

Aldara, Technical Project Manager and Project Engineer in Sener's Offshore Wind Department

The main barriers to the deployment of floating offshore wind turbines (FOWT) are both non-technical and technical. Non-technical barriers include high costs due to high initial voltage, high levelized cost of electricity (LCOE), and high manufacturing and export costs. In addition, government support is insufficient, with the need for subsidies, incentives and a favourable regulatory framework currently hampering investment and project development. Supply chain constraints are also significant, with delays and high costs, and limited availability of adequate installation infrastructure.

On the technical side, non-technological barriers include financing and public support, cooperation risks, regulations and permits, and political influence at local, regional and national levels. Technological barriers include the need for specialised components, advanced modelling and the development of pilot and test innovations. There is also a need for advanced design and optimisation tools, including the use of machine learning and plan modelling, and advances in control systems. Integration barriers include holistic network design, flexibility requirements, storage and hybrid systems.

Non-technical enablers include grants and subsidies, low-interest loans, green funds and climate bonds, effective communication, co-financing, feed-in tariffs, power purchase agreements and public commitments. Technical enablers include a competitive market, innovation in new technologies, grid integration flexibility, marine hybrid systems, supply chain improvements, grid reinforcement, proper planning and permitting, and a clear route to market.

3 ROUNDTABLES TOPICS OVERVIEW

After the presentations, the stage was set for the final debate. The moderator took the lead, facilitating questions and ensuring that all participants had the opportunity to express their views. The Mentimeter tool was used primarily to open up questions that could then be debated and explored further. The ideas and solutions that emerged from the debate were:

The **current regulatory framework is seen as a barrier rather than an enabler** to the development of renewable energy. Detailed and problem-solving regulations are essential to move forward. The **Royal Decree, once published, could become a facilitator** by allowing work to begin, but greater interconnection capacity is needed.

Social acceptance is crucial for the success of projects. Raising awareness and demonstrating the benefits are essential to overcome barriers and gain social acceptance.

Environmental legislation must be a priority in any planning phase, and the importance of separating visual and environmental impacts is discussed. In places like the Canary Islands, the visible presence of windfarms can be a tool to promote sustainable tourism.

Port logistics and infrastructure development are major challenges, and offshore wind projects need to include appropriate decommissioning plans. Resistance to change and the need to raise public awareness of the importance of renewable energy are major obstacles.

The benefits of offshore wind can be quantifiable, such as positive impacts on property values, **and non-quantifiable**, such as social acceptance and perceptions of change. Distinguishing between these types of impacts is crucial to moving forward with project implementation.

It is generally accepted that offshore wind farms can have a **positive impact on local economic activities and the environment**. Local communities should be involved in the planning and development of these projects.

4 CO-CREATION ACTIVITIES

To conclude the event, the Mentimeter tool was used to record the baseline questions from all Marine Wind workshops at the various locations.

1. Which of the following categories represents you?

The figure shows a pie chart representing the categories of participants. The majority of participants come from companies (56%), followed in decreasing order by universities (24%), research organisations (12%), institutions (4%) and others (4%).

Figure 1 MENTIMETER. Question 1

2. How much impact are floating offshore wind farms likely to have on local economic activities (e.g. fishing, tourism) in your opinion?

Regarding the impact of farms on local activity, there is a well-diversified range of opinions. No one thinks that the impact will be strongly negative, but we observe that a third of the participants think that the impact can be negative, of which almost half think that the negative impact will be moderate. The other two thirds think that the impact will be positive. We find that these participants, the positive impact participants, are also very well distributed, with a third in the position of thinking that the impact will be moderate and another third in the position of thinking that the impact will be very

strong. Only two participants think that the impact will be neutral, that is 7%, so we can conclude that this way of thinking will not be predominant.

Figure 2 MENTIMETER. Question 2

3. How much impact could have Floating Offshore Wind Farms on environment?

On this question, in contrast to the previous one, we find that the vast majority of people think that the environmental impact will be neither positive nor negative, or moderately negative. The next large group of positions, 25%, are those who think that the impact will be moderately positive or strongly negative, split about equally.

Figure 3 MENTIMETER. Question 3

4. Do you think that Offshore Wind Farms can benefit local community?

The survey results indicate that people think that the construction of the OWF will bring prosperity to the local community, only the 25% of them are not strongly decided if the effects will be positive, but still accept that the effects will be positive.

Figure 4 MENTIMETER. Question 4

5. Do you think that your OWF awareness has improved due to your participation in MARINEWIND co-creation labs?

The vast majority responded that the co-creation labs had been useful to them. They say that these labs have helped them to improve their awareness of the OWF. 20% of them expressed that this co-creation lab has improved their awareness a lot, while the other 80% are not so enthusiastic about their improvement. 25% of the participants said that this lab did not make any difference in their thinking about OWF, it is also possible that these people were already very conscientious about the importance of OWF before coming to this event, so most of them work in companies that develop these farms. This thought will also apply to the next two questions from the moderator.

Figure 6 MENTIMETER. Question 5

6. Do you think that your knowledge has increased after your co-creation lab MARINEWIND participation?

The findings in this study are similar to the previous one regarding knowledge improvement, with one distinction: more participants reported that this workshop did not enhance their understanding of offshore wind farms. While many individuals did not significantly increase their knowledge, the majority still gained some insights from the workshop.

Figure 7 MENTIMETER. Question 6

7. Do you think that your social acceptance and environmental impact has increased after your co-creation lab MARINEWIND participation?

For the most part, people did not change much in their opinion of social acceptance after this lab. This makes sense, as most of the participants had already expressed their support for the OWF constructions before the Mentimeter questions. 25% of the participants said that their acceptance of the OWF had improved.

Figure 8 MENTIMETER. Question 7

5 SUMMARY OF IDENTIFIED BARRIERS AND ENABLERS

This Co-Creation Workshop delved not only into the barriers hindering the deployment of offshore wind energy in Spain but also heavily focused on determining the necessary measures to facilitate this deployment, taking into account the resources available in Catalunya. As a culmination of the entire session, the following key milestones were clearly identified:

BARRIERS	ENABLERS
<p>Role of public administration and dialogue facilitation: Lack of proactive promotion of dialogue by public administrations, leading to frustration among participants about insufficient support for societal acceptance.</p> <p>Government involvement and support: Lack of government representation and effective decision-making in offshore wind farm projects, leading to stakeholder frustration.</p>	<p>Encourage governments to engage in early dialogue and facilitate transparent communication to build social acceptance and common ground.</p> <p>Recognising the key role of strong governance and commitment from all stakeholders and emphasising the need for government involvement and support to overcome challenges and ensure project success.</p>
<p>Impact on fisheries: Lack of transparency and cooperation between the fisheries and renewable energy sectors, hindering dialogue and data sharing.</p>	<p>Coexistence and cooperation: Focus on fostering equal conditions for coexistence and promoting positive intersectoral relations through dialogue facilitation and new integrated models.</p>
<p>Lack of marine spatial planning: Marine spatial planning needs to be concise and specific to ensure good use and stakeholder confidence in the development process and the coexistence of different activities in the sea.</p>	<p>Communicating with experienced specialists: In order to achieve special marine planning, experts in the field need to be heard. Enabling communication with stakeholders will make it easier to identify barriers.</p>
<p>Infrastructure limitations and cost concerns: Lack of adequate space and port infrastructure for offshore wind deployment, compounded by high costs and infrastructure limitations.</p>	<p>Advocate for investment in infrastructure development and cost reduction strategies to address deployment challenges.</p>
<p>Social acceptance: Today, social acceptance is still a barrier, as people still believe that OWFs have a negative impact on the local environment and economy.</p>	<p>Transparency of information: A large part of the lack of social acceptance comes from people not being aware of the studies that specialists have done and prove that the project will benefit them. We need to be more transparent with the project and explain to people who are not aware of OWF's.</p>
<p>Decommissioning plans: There is no regulation, no explanation of how the project will be decommissioned. There is nothing about what to do when the life of the OWFs is over.</p>	<p>Create a stronger framework: Create a section that talks about the decommissioning process.</p>
<p>Lack of information/experience with the technology: There is a fear of this new technology because there is not much information about its effects.</p>	<p>Test periods to try out the technology: These trial periods will give us real information about their behaviour.</p>